

[Hernia Kit | Best Ayurvedic Medicine For Hernia Pain](#)

What Is A Hernia ?

A common definition of hernia is a bulging of a tissue or organ through an abnormal opening. In Ayurveda a hernia is described as a tissue rupture due to swelling in the intestine. As the pressure increases on inside wall of organ with passage of time, the abdominal wall becomes weak. It results in a rupture which leads to further complications if remains untreated.

Your intestines push through the muscle wall where a gap is created, causing pain and discomfort. Ayurveda classifies all these types of hernias as similar in nature because they are due to inflammation of the intestine. [A hernia usually happens in the abdominal area](#). The pain associated with a hernia can affect many aspects of your work and personal life, limiting your activities and quality of lifestyle.

Hernia Kit:
Best Ayurvedic Hernia Treatment Without Surgery
Grocare®'s Hernia Kit is designed to Cure Hernia Without Surgery.
Website: <https://in.grocare.com/> Tel: +91-9822100031

At Grocare®, we care for you much more than you care for yourselves. Grocare®'s Hernia Kit is designed to Cure Hernia Without Surgery.

Each 40 Day Kit Contains:

Hernica® - 1 Bottle of 160 Tablets

Acidim® - 2 Bottles of 160 Tablets

We developed Hernica® and Acidim® after years of research & hard work - which together help in curing Hernia without surgery.

A) [Hernica:](#)

The active ingredients are:

Pongamia glabra: This plant has a chemical substance known as karanjin. It has strong anti-inflammatory and healing effects. It provides a great relief from hernia pain and also helps to repair the damaged layer.

Cassia angustifolia: This plant contains glycosides called sennosides A and B. These glycosides work as laxatives and aid the digestion issues such as gas, constipation and bloating.

Holarrhena antidysenterica: This is used as a digestive aid to treat issues like diarrhea, constipation and colic. It also works as an antispasmodic agent. All these ailments worsen the hernia symptoms therefore, it is given to patients to avoid complications.

Ferula asafoetida: This plant has strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Therefore, helps to decrease the inflammation related to hiatal hernia. It also works as an antispasmodic agent and emmenagogue.

B) [Acidim:](#)

The main active ingredients in this are:

Ipomea turpethum: This plant tends to have laxative and cathartic properties. Therefore, used as a digestive aid in people with IBD and hernia.

Eugenia caryophyllata: This is also known as clove and possesses some essential oils and vitamin A and C which are very effective antioxidants and prevent and treat digestive problems and hernia repair.

Cyperus rotundus: This plant also has antioxidant properties which give a protective effect to the abdominal lining to repair hernia and other stomach issues.

Emblica ribes: This is also known as false black pepper and has potent anti-bacterial, anti-flatulence and antiprotozoal activities. Therefore, it is included in this formula to treat digestive ailments such as gas, bloating, inflammation which may worsen the hernia symptoms.

TIMELINE:

Initial symptoms should subside within a few weeks. Visible changes in hernia are noticeable around 4th month. After approximately 5 months, the hernia should become soft, and then begin to subside. In most cases, results are achieved within 6 to 8 months.

If the neck of the hernia is larger than 7mm, it may be recommended to wear a hernia belt, once the swelling of the intestine subsides; typically from month 4th onward. This helps to reinforce the abdominal wall during recovery.

The timeline may vary from person to person, depending on the severity of the disease, diet and lifestyle. Suggestions will be emailed to make the best of the kit.

For More Details About Hernia And To Order Online, You Can Go To

<https://in.grocare.com/products/hernia-kit>